

BUSINESS MODEL FOR SPECIAL TRADITIONAL DRINKS OF GRESIK'S IN CURCUMA AND GINGER POTION "ESON"

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Abstract

The culinary business in Gresik Regency requires attention from at least local stakeholders, not only because of the high consumer interest in its culinary specialties but also because the market for these products is also becoming crowded and saturated. Meanwhile, the potential of this business is actually still vast, supported by the spirit of preserving local wisdom. Another problem that also arises is the level of business competition is also quite high. This study aims to determine how the BMC concept for MSEs practices in Gresik Regency. The focus of this study is to conduct observations on businesses in the culinary sector, specifically traditional beverages, such as sinom and temulawak "Eson". The results of this study revealed that the business model in this business is feasible with several recommendations regarding business management and networking, which require adaptation and alignment with current business developments. The empathy map as a business model tool shows a positive image of consumers or those who are satisfied with the product. However, in an effort to increase sales levels, marketing improvements are needed as a key to business success. Product quality is known to be good, but innovation in new flavors is possible, such as: adding different, contemporary ingredients, so that it can be an alternative to expand the market for traditional beverage products typical of Gresik Regency.

Keywords: *Curcuma & Ginger, BMC, Emphaty Map, Micro and Small Enterprises*

INTRODUCTION

Gresik Regency boasts a diverse culinary scene that attracts both locals and visitors. Each culinary specialty offers unique dishes and beverages that reflect the region's identity or promote local wisdom. Furthermore, Gresik's culinary traditions reflect the region's diverse culture and civilization. Gresik's culinary traditions are known to possess unique flavors that distinguish them from other regional cuisines. Gresik's culinary businesses offer considerable potential, as the city boasts both tourism and industrial potential and adequate infrastructure to support the growth of businesses in the region (Santoso et al., 2025). The scale of Gresik's culinary specialty businesses is dominated by micro and small industries, as these businesses are usually run from generation to generation, while enthusiasts of these specialty culinary delights are also native residents of Gresik Regency. Among the various types of culinary specialty of Gresik Regency, one of the specialty culinary delights is the traditional drink typical of Gresik Regency which is widely loved by residents of all ages, namely: sinom and temulawak. These sinom and temulawak products are made from raw materials from the rhizomes of plants that have many health benefits. Considering that many people like these drinks for health reasons, there are also many sinom and temulawak business actors in Gresik Regency.

Some products are often marketed, both in markets, stalls, shops, restaurants, and supermarkets. Various product brands are available for this product. Likewise, this specialty drink business is also available in online, both marketplaces or social media. Ease of entry into the culinary market has increased competition in this business sector (Vuksanović et al., 2024). Difficulty obtaining raw materials and the high price of ingredients for this traditional beverage from Gresik Regency pose challenges. However, the resilient nature of Gresik Regency entrepreneurs has not deterred them from pursuing this venture, ensuring the continuity of the business they have established. Meanwhile, the low level of business in this traditional beverage industry from Gresik Regency has resulted in relatively small capital, which has limited business operations. Thus, the challenge facing this business is limited capital. Nearly all micro and small business owners have less than a college degree, and some even have only a junior

high school diploma. This limited educational attainment among micro and small business owners, and their inactivity in participating in business-based training, often leads to a monotonous business culture, or a lack of significant innovation within their businesses. Furthermore, the administration and management of micro and small business owners are often poorly organized and well-organized (Abebe & Kegne, 2023). In many cases, businesses fail to separate personal and business assets, leading to potential business losses that can impact the family's financial well-being. The focus of this research is to examine the business strategy of traditional beverages typical of Gresik Regency, specifically business actors of the product type: *sinom* or *temulawak* with the brand "Eson". The *sinom* and *temulawak* "Eson" business is a business that was passed down from the previous generation or family business. However, in its development has undergone innovation to suit the consumer tastes of Gresik Regency residents. The business run by Mr. "Fahmi" was passed down from his parents with *temulawak* drinks packaged in glass bottles from recycled tea drinks. In 2006, he developed a traditional drink, *sinom*, in plastic packaging.

The characteristics of the "Eson" *sinom* and *temulawak* business are almost identical to the challenges faced by other micro and small businesses, namely marketing and capital issues. As a result, the business struggles to reach the international market that many established entrepreneurs dream of. Weak marketing stems from their inability to build a broad market network due to their limited business relationships. Meanwhile, their limited capital makes "Eson" *sinom* entrepreneurs unable to increase production capacity when there is an increase in product demand. In fact, "Eson" *sinom* should be able to meet the high market demand. The frequent increase in the number of employees at certain times to anticipate market demand indicates that this business is progressing well (Kajtazi et al., 2023). The various problems faced by the "Eson" business require the determination of a suitable practical business model to anticipate the dynamics of the business with various business challenges faced. The business model that demonstrates stakeholder involvement in business implementation to support business sustainability (Kajtazi et al., 2023). There are two types of business models that will be analyzed in this study, namely: the canvas business model and the empathy map. The canvas business model maps the business into nine components, while the empathy map shows the understanding of consumer insight into the products (*sinom* & *temulawak*) "Eson".

The design and creation of a business model are crucial to a company's operational success. A business model differentiates one company from another, and it can create competitive advantage. Considering the challenges, opportunities, and constraints, it's crucial to reevaluate all business processes and activities using the business model. Each element on the canvas has varying degrees of influence on a company's success (Ladd, 2018). A set of activities in a business intended to create added value, mapped as a business model, shows how the processes and business are run. A business model describes the entire business and its activities and how the business operates to create value, revealing the business logic (Carter & Carter, 2020). Based on the two main problems in the "Eson" *sinom*, the purpose of this study is to analyze the business model and redesign a simple model that supports business development in micro-scale business practices for the traditional beverage sector of Gresik Regency through the following approaches: first, using BMC; second, describing the Empathy Map. Research that examines the application of methods *Business Model Canvas* The research conducted by the Gresik Traditional Beverage Business "Sinom Eson" is expected to provide new insights into business development. The results of this research are expected to provide practical benefits for community members in identifying new opportunities, addressing existing challenges, optimizing their business strategies, and enhancing the community's competitiveness in the face of increasingly fierce business competition. Challenges, opportunities and constraints, so it is important to re-evaluate the entire business process and overall activities using a business model.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature Review

Strategy Management

Strategic management in the context of MSMEs explains how companies create and maintain competitive advantage (Maijanen, 2020). Business sustainability is supported by a company's ability in strategic management.

Business Model Canvas

A business model describes the entire business and its activities and how the business operates to create value, revealing business logic (Carter & Carter, 2020). BMC is a series of activities in a company aimed at creating added value that is mapped as a business model showing how the process and business are run. A business model describes the entire business and its activities and how the business operates to create value, revealing business logic (Carter & Carter, 2020). BMC is a tool that shows the steps to achieve business goals, the parties involved and the requirements needed in the business so that, Elements of the Business Model Canvas, include:

1. Segmentation: customers are divided into groups of individuals who are similar in certain categories, such as age,

gender, interests, and shopping habits.

2. Value Proposition: Benefits of using *value proposition canvas* antara lain: (Osterwalder et al., 2015) is a canvas created to describe two values: the value of the product or service we provide to customers and the value of the problems customers desire. The value proposition canvas is two parts of the business model canvas: value proposition and customer segment. With this canvas, companies can determine what customers want and what they least want. Furthermore, this canvas has a function to ensure there is a fit between the product and the market by exploring the relationship between customer needs and the company's value proposition.
 - a. New value in meeting customer needs
 - b. Performance offers improved performance after using your product or service.
 - c. Customization, namely making products according to special requests from customers.
 - d. Getting the Job Done is added value for customers when solving their problems.
 - e. Design is not only a tangible or intangible product.
 - f. Brand/status. enables customers to find added value in improving their social status.
 - g. Business advantages related to setting prices according to the characteristics of the target customers.
 - h. Providing customer value in the form of: reducing costs from activities carried out by customers.
 - i. Providing benefits to customers by reducing the risks experienced by customers
3. Channels: how to reach customer segments from start to finish.
4. Interaction with Customers: the company is able to build bonds with its customers.
5. Product Activities generate value propositions
6. Main Resources, starting from managing raw materials, controlling stock of goods, arranging human resources, and arranging operational processes.
 - a. Physical Resources: physical assets required for business activities to operate optimally.
 - b. Intellectual Resources: are "company secrets" in nature to be able to progress and survive.
 - c. Human resources: all kinds of knowledge, skills and human competencies needed to make the business run well, whether on a permanent, contract or daily basis.
 - d. Financial Resources: all financial resources needed for business operations
 - e. Technology Resources & Methods: methods that function to support product excellence
7. Partnership: stakeholders must be identified first so they can provide positive benefits for the business.
 - a. Alliance Strategy; Cooperation with businesses that are not similar or not competitors.
 - b. Cooperation: Cooperation with competing companies.
 - c. Joint Venture: Collaboration to form a new business
 - d. Buyer and Supplier Relationship: Cooperation is limited to buyers and sellers.
8. Source of Income: in increasing the number of sales outside of its main activities.
 - 1) Operating Income: obtained through the company's sales of goods.
 - a) Transaction Based Revenue
 - b) Revenue from Services
 - c) Revenue from Projects
 - d) Recurring revenue: ongoing payments from customers
 - 2) Non-Operational Income: obtained from sources other than core business activities
 - a) Originated from company investments
 - b) Derived from share ownership
 - c) Passive Income from land or equipment
9. Cost Structure: the costs of creating excellence, interacting with, and retaining customers.
 - a. Fixed Costs
 - b. Variable Costs
 - c. Economies of scale: the cost advantages a business enjoys as its production expands
 - d. Economies of scope: cost advantages enjoyed due to larger operational scope

Business strength stems from the ability of the actor to develop the existing business. Purwadhi et al. (2022) defines business development as the process of advancing a business to a point where the company can provide goods and services to all external parties who need them. Business development by micro-industry actors is often hampered by several business weaknesses, such as: the unavailability of business premises to market products, the quality of human resources that are poorly trained and hinder the production process, and weaknesses in financial management (Istiqomah & Andriyanto, 2018). Business development from a company marketing perspective is a promotional

process to build and maintain working relationships related to business goals. In developing a business, Syahidin & Ramadhan (2022) explain that the stages passed are: new business ideas, idea screening, business plan development, and business control.

Empathy Map

Besides BMC, Empathy Map is also another business modeling tool.

Empathy maps are a tool used by teams to collaborate to gain a deeper understanding of users/customers and their behaviors, attitudes, and needs. Empathy maps expand users' knowledge to create a shared understanding of their needs and aid decision-making. Empathy maps are excellent for identifying and identifying problems faced by others, as they can yield in-depth insights. Four quadrants of the empathy map are analyzed:

a) **Quadrant Says**

Verbatim and direct quotes from users regarding the problems they face to find the problems they most want to solve.

b) **Thinks Quadrant**

Interpretation of users' thoughts throughout their experience and paying special attention to what users think, but may not be able to convey/are unwilling to voice.

c) **Does Quadrant**

User behavior is something a user physically does, or does, to resolve a problem they are facing and have not yet been able to resolve. A reference to a step that was not used due to a failure to meet the user's needs.

d) **Feels Quadrant**

The emotional state of the user is displayed in the form of adjectives, such as: excited, worried, or feeling

METHOD

Research Design

The study uses a quantitative approach with a phenomenological type. This study seeks to understand the views of business actors regarding the practice of business models in traditional beverage businesses in Gresik Regency, especially for product types, specifically: sinom and temulawak under the brand "Eson" which has been established for approximately ten years. The study was conducted at a micro-business of traditional beverages in Gresik Regency owned by Mr. Fahmi and located in Manyar District, Gresik Regency. Structured interviews were conducted with the owner, agents, and also consumers of traditional beverage products typical of Gresik. The flow of this research includes several stages of data management, namely: reduction, presentation, conclusion, and verification (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Analysis Techniques

The analysis technique used in this study was a narrative SWOT analysis. The focus of this study was to explore the components of the BMC in depth. Next, a SWOT analysis was conducted to understand the internal and external factors of micro-enterprises. The business's position within the SWOT quadrants will determine an effective strategy for achieving its business goals. Finally, an Empathy Map analysis was conducted to understand the perspectives of consumers of "Eson" sinom and temulawak.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research finding reveals the types of business modeling

1. BMC Exploration of Traditional Gresik Drinks (Sinom & Temulawak) "Eson"

The components of the BMC are mapped based on observations and correspondence at different times with various stakeholders, such as owners, agents, and consumers. Figure 1 shows the Business Model Canvas.

Figure 1. Business Model Canvas

Source: processed data, 2024

Each component of the BMC can be explained as follows:

a. Customer Segments

The traditional sinom and temulawak drink "Eson" attracts both teenagers and adults/elderly customers. Teenagers range in age from 13 to 19, while adults/elderly consumers range in age from 20 to 70. Even consumers over 70 consume this drink for health reasons.

b. Value Proposition

The value offered by sinom and temulawak products lies in their flavor, which meets consumer preferences because they are made with quality ingredients. Furthermore, they are made without preservatives, thus maintaining freshness and a longer shelf life. Customers generally experience health benefits from consuming one or both of these drinks due to the beneficial spices they contain. In addition to these benefits, the products are also affordable. The packaging is varied, allowing consumers to purchase according to their needs. The products are readily available everywhere, including in...store.

c. Channel

"Eson" beverage products are marketed both offline and online. Offline sales involve sales in stores, stalls, and restaurants, while online marketing primarily utilizes Facebook as a promotional medium. Orders are also accepted through WhatsApp.

d. Customer Relations

The "Eson" product builds customer relationships by leveraging online social media for promotions. To introduce traditional beverages and attract new customers, sinom and temulawak are featured at public events that attract many customers. Other customer relationship strategies include offering discounts on product purchases. This business welcomes criticism and suggestions.

e. Income Stream

Revenue flows from sales revenue. Furthermore, a percentage of the profit is earned through collaboration between sales representatives. Sinom "Eson" also offers business opportunities, such as becoming a product agent, where revenue flows from traditional beverage agents in each village. Participation in activities opens up opportunities for increased sales.

f. Key Resources

The traditional beverage business "Eson" has two types of resources: physical and non-physical. Physical resources include raw materials (sugar, turmeric, Javanese ginger, and ginger), equipment, workers, a shop,

a production facility, and a payment transaction system. Non-physical resources include intellectual capital, business knowledge and experience, branding, a logo, and social media accounts. Meanwhile, financial resources include cash.

g. Key Activities

Some of the key activities of the "Eson" business include: searching and purchasing raw materials from several regions to obtain the best quality, processing products with special blends for a unique and consistent taste with longer product durability, packaging, creating content and promotional posts for social media, being active in association activities and service exhibitions, as well as strengthening cooperation and networking to add sales agents and find buyers.

h. Key Partnerships

There are several key partners in the "Eson" business, namely: farmers, suppliers of rhizome roots as raw materials for traditional drinks (sinom and temulawak), guards, store, sales agents, services, business associations of Gresik Regency

i. Cost Structure

The prices of "Eson" brand sinom and temulawak are affordable. The costs involved in the "Eson" sinom and temulawak business are fixed and variable. These include internet costs, production house costs, and...store, equipment, promotion costs, and maintenance costs are fixed costs, while variable costs include: packaging costs, labor costs, raw material costs.

2. Empathy Map Model Identification

Empathy map based on consumer views on the "Eson" sinom and temulawak business. Figure 2 below shows a representation of the Empathy Map on the "Eson" Business.

Figure 2. "Eson" Empathy Map

Source: processed data, 2024

Elements of an empathy map include (Akbari et al., 2025):

a. What Do Consumers Say About "Eson" Products?

Consumers' perceptions of what they saw when they visited and tasted sinom or temulawak (Indonesian traditional Javanese ginger) labeled "Eson" (Indonesian traditional Javanese ginger) were authentic beverages from Gresik Regency, with a distinct flavor compared to similar drinks from other regions. They also noted the product's hygienic appearance from the packaging. Furthermore, they noted that the store selling "Eson" products was neatly organized and attractive.

b. What Do Consumers Think About "Eson" Products?

Consumers believe that "Eson" sinom and temulawak products are widely available. They believe the products are affordable, with their quality and distinctive spice flavor. Furthermore, they believe the products come in a variety of packaging options, tailored to their needs.

c. What do consumers feel about the "Eson" product?

Consumers find the "Eson" sinom and temulawak products to have a smooth, non-irritating sensation. They've

tried several different brands of sinom and temulawak, but found the taste to be harsh on the throat. Consumers also report that consuming this traditional beverage leaves them feeling refreshed and, if they're feeling unwell, quickly recovers.

d. What Do Consumers Do With "Eson" Products?

Consumers' attitudes after visiting the store include positive recommendations for "Eson" products to potential customers. Some consumers conveyed their positive impressions through positive responses in social media posts on the "Eson" business account or by posting product photos or videos on their personal accounts. However, there were also loyal consumers who consistently purchased products but did not provide recommendations to potential buyers.

Furthermore, a description of consumer insight into the sinom and temulawak products "Eson" is represented through an empathy map to help entrepreneurs in traditional beverages from Gresik Regency in developing their businesses and offering innovations so that consumers will repurchase "Eson" products. The four components of the empathy map, namely: words, feelings, thoughts, and actions show positive results. Thus, consumers feel satisfied and enjoy the "Eson" products.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of business practices of the traditional beverage business typical of Gresik Regency, namely "Eson" with the canvas business model approach and empathy map, it is known that the "Eson" business actor has run the business well. However, it still needs a business model and also a strategy that supports business progress so that the "Eson" sinom and temulawak business can increase its business scale and build its business even bigger so that the "Eson" brand can become a pioneer among several other traditional beverage brands typical of "Gresik Regency". The reference suggestion for the "Eson" business in the canvas business model is to improve financial administration more systematically so that business governance is better. Another recommendation is to increase business networks in order to continue to expand the market, for example inviting students to be involved in their business, such as: helping with business administration or helping as business partners.

A positive empathy map result indicates that the product meets consumer expectations, but requires further marketing development, such as collaborating with catering companies to increase sales and hire more employees. There's also the possibility of adding new product variants or flavors to existing products, or incorporating new ingredients and recipes that suit current tastes, allowing consumers to create a wider selection of products. This study is limited by its focus on only one type of traditional beverage business in Gresik Regency and its lack of comparison with other similar businesses. It also focuses solely on the business model canvas with an empathy map, and it is possible to link business practices with Porter's forces, QSPM analysis, or SWOT analysis.

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